

A STUDY ON CHANGING DIRECTIONS ON INDIAN COFFEE EXPORT

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Abstract:

Coffee is a major export commodity in developing country like India. Liberalization Of coffee market has given rise to the competition and to services in this competition to Market newer. New strategies are being made to make the products stable in the market are being made. The government has to provide more subsidies and schemes for the Benefits of exports to make their business more active in the market. The service providers Middle man and the agencies are to be regularized.

Key Words: Coffee, Service Provider & Export

Introduction and Design of the Study:

Coffee is a large genus containing more than 90 species of flowering plants in the family Rubiaceae. They are shrubs or small trees native to subtropical Africa and southern Asia. Seed of several species are the source of the beverage coffee. The coffee plant is a woody perennial evergreen and because it grows to a relatively large height, it is more accurately described as a coffee dicotyledon tree. The seeds are called beans in the trade. Coffee beans are widely cultivated in tropical countries in plantations for both local consumption and export to temperate countries. Coffee ranks as one of the world's major commodity crops and is the major export product of some countries. Coffee production in Brazil is responsible for about a third of all coffee making Brazil by for the largest producer, a position the country has held for the last 150 years.

Coffee is not native to the Americas and had to be planted in the country. The first coffee bush in Brazil was planted by Francisco de Melo Palheta in the state of Para in 1727. Coffee was introduced in Brazil by the Portuguese in the 19th century. Coffee is a brewed beverage with a dark, acidic flavor prepared from the roasted seeds of the coffee plant, colloquially called coffee beans. Plant diseases, soil erosion, climatic fluctuations and careless picking are some problems faced by the coffee growers.

Coffee beans were first exported from Ethiopia to Yemen. Yemeni traders brought coffee back to their homeland and began to cultivate the bean. The word Qahwa originally meant wine, coffee moved from Yemen to Mekka to Egypt and Turkey. Coffee was first introduced to Europe in the island of Malta in the 16th century by Turkey people. Coffee is a brewed drink prepared from roasted coffee beans, which are the seeds of berries from the coffee plant. The plant is native to subtropical Africa and some islands in southern Asia. The plant was exported from Africa to countries around the world and coffee plants are now cultivated in over 70 countries. Coffee is one of the most popular drinks in the world. It can be prepared and presented in a variety of ways espresso, cappuccino, café latte etc.

Statement of the Problem:

The production of coffee and the coffee board focusses on the use of coffee and how it has changed over the years and how cafes have become hugely popular across India. Coffee is an integral part of our system and it has been a part of our history also. It is served as a relieving beverage and is used by everyone. Coffee is of many types from hot coffee to cold coffee. Coffee offers a zippy tang which is driving factors in its success. It has become vital in our everyday lifestyle regardless of its type. Coffee has lot of types and all of them have their specific taste. Starting from hot coffee to cappuccino, to cold coffee and every coffee has its own specific use. The international coffee board are restricted the use of coffee to be used for constructive process such as making healthy coffee.

Hot beverages have been always been a part of tradition in India, especially South India. Coffee took the first seat in South India when the traditional Brahmin classes brought down the beverage from the ruling British around 1930s.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the worldwide performance of coffee industry.
- ✓ To study the position of coffee industry in the Indian scenario.
- ✓ To compare the growth of coffee exports over the past five years.
- ✓ To study the technological up gradation in the industry.
- ✓ To sort out the problems faced by coffee exporters in India.
- ✓ To create awareness on the various incentives and support structure from government.

- ✓ To suggest measures.

Research Methodology:

Research is an endeavor to discover answers to intellectual and practical problems through the application of scientific method. Research is a systematized effort to gain more knowledge. Research is a systematic process of collecting and analyzing information in order to increase our understanding of the phenomenon about which are concerned or interested. It is an art of scientific investigation. Research is the search for knowledge, using objective and systematic methods to find solution to the problem.

Data Collection: The primary data is collected with the help of structured questionnaire.

Sampling: Convenient sampling is used for Data collection.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

A Systematic examination and evaluation of data and information by breaking it into its component parts to uncover their relationships. An examination of data and facts to uncover and understand cause effect relationships thus providing basis for problem solving and decision making. Interpretation is an act of explaining, reframing, or otherwise showing own understanding of something. A person who translates one language into another is called an interpreter.

Statistical Tools Used: Simple percentage analysis and Chi-square

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is consigned to Tamil Nadu region.
- ✓ Data collection limitations.
- ✓ Lack of structured organizational structure.
- ✓ Limited published data.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Percentage Analysis:

Out of the total respondents, 27.3% have less than 5 years of experience in Coffee export, 45.5% have 6 -10 years of experience and 27.3% have 11 to 15 years of experience.

Overseas Marketers Prefer for Export Coffee:

Out of the total respondents,9.1% natural of the product handied,36.4% customer Base available, 9.1% product lines engaged into, 18.2%financial resources,9.1% particular Out of the total respondents,9.1% natural of the product handied,36.4% customer Base available, 9.1% product lines engaged into, 18.2%financial resources,9.1% particular Marketing strength, 9.1% cooperation offered,9.1% experience in the line. Marketing strength, 9.1% cooperation offered, 9.1% experience in the line.

Prepare Generally in Your Export Transaction:

Out of the total respondents, 9.1% payment in advance, 18.2% open account.36.4% documentary bills, 27.3% documentary credit under letter of credit, 9.1% shipment on Consignment basis.

Components of Export Price & Most Important for Coffee:

Out of the total respondents, 36.4% special packaging cost, 54.5% transport cost, 9.1% storage cost. Components of export price and most important for coffee.

Inco Terms do you Prefer to Quote Export Price:

Out of the total respondents, 9.1% FAS, 63.6% FOB, 18.2% C&F, 9.1% CIF. Inco terms do you prefer to quote export price

Satisfied with the Services of Clearing and Forwarding Agents:

Out of the total respondents, 36.4% extremely satisfied, 45.5% moderately satisfied, 9.1% average satisfied, 9.1% extremely satisfied with the services of clearing and forwarding agents.

Services of Various Government Agencies Assisting in Export Business:

Out of the total respondents, 36.4% extremely satisfied, 63.3% moderately satisfied with the Services of various government agencies assisting in export business.

Chisqaure Analysis:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and Source of supply used for procuring items for exporting.

Using Chi-Square

Calculated value = .727

Table Value = 5.99

If calculated value < Table value, H₀ is accepted

If Calculated value > Table value, H₀ is rejected

Since the calculated value < Table value, H₀ is accepted.

There is no significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and Source of supply used for procuring items for exporting.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and Factors for supplier selection.

Using Chi-Square,

Calculated value = 7.364

Table Value = 5.99

If calculated value < Table value, H₀ is accepted

If Calculated value > Table value, H₀ is rejected

Since the calculated value > Table value, H₀ is rejected.

There is significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and Factors for supplier selection.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and tie up with Business units.

Using Chi-Square,

Calculated value = 2.273

Table Value = 5.99

If calculated value < Table value, H₀ is accepted

If Calculated value > Table value, H₀ is rejected

Since the calculated value < Table value, H₀ is accepted.

There is no significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and tie up with Business units.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and kind of processing unit.

Using Chi-Square,

Calculated value = 4.455

Table Value = 5.99

If calculated value < Table value, H₀ is accepted

If Calculated value > Table value, H₀ is rejected

Since the calculated value < Table value, H₀ is accepted.

There is no significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and kind of processing unit.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and methods of payment.

Using Chi-Square,

Calculated value = 0.99

Table Value = 5.99

If calculated value < Table value, H₀ is accepted

If Calculated value > Table value, H₀ is rejected

Since the calculated value < Table value, H₀ is accepted.

There is no significant relationship between Number of years in Coffee Export and methods of payment.

Findings:

- ✓ Out of the total respondents, 27.3% have less than 5 years of experience in Coffee export, 45.5% have 6 -10 years of experience and 27.3% have 11 to 15 years of experience.
- ✓ Out of the total respondents, 9.1% natural of the product handled, 36.4% customer Base available, 9.1% product lines engaged into, 18.2% financial resources, 9.1% particular Marketing strength, 9.1% cooperation offered, 9.1% experience in the line.
- ✓ Out of the total respondents, 27.3% prefer pre-shipment, 54.5% post shipment and 18.2% forfeiting.
- ✓ Out of the total respondents, 9.1% payment in advance, 18.2% open account, 36.4% documentary bills, 27.3% documentary credit under letter of credit, 9.1% shipment on Consignment basis.
- ✓ Out of the total respondents, 36.4% special packaging cost, 54.5% transport cost, 9.1% storage cost. components of export price and most important for coffee.
- ✓ Out of the total respondents, 9.1% FAS, 63.6% FOB, 18.2% C&F, 9.1% CIF. Incoterms do you prefer to quote export price.
- ✓ Out of the total respondents, 36.4% extremely satisfied, 45.5% moderately satisfied, 9.1% average satisfied, 9.1% extremely satisfied. With the services of clearing and Forwarding agents.

Suggestions:

- ✓ If the government provides introduces more schemes for this , It will be more Helpful for the business to make more services.
- ✓ The 36.4% the respondent were extremely satisfied with the services.
- ✓ The clearing and forwarding agents have to identify the need of the exporters And serve them accordingly.
- ✓ The government has to make more subsidies and schemes for the benefit Of the exporters.

Conclusion:

New strategies are being made to make the products stable in the market are being made. The government has to provide more subsidies and schemes for the Benefits of exports to make their business more active in the market. The service providers Middle man and the agencies are to be regularized.

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